

SUSTAINED REDUCTION OF BLOOD CULTURE CONTAMINATION USING A NURSE-LED ASEPTIC BUNDLE: A THREE-YEAR QUALITY IMPROVEMENT STUDY IN A PEDIATRIC EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT IN OMAN

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Abstract

Objective

To evaluate the impact of a nurse-led aseptic technique bundle on pediatric blood culture contamination (BCC) rates over three years.

Methods

A quasi-experimental before–after quality improvement study was conducted in the Pediatric Emergency Department at Royal Hospital, Oman (January 2022–December 2024). A nurse-led bundle comprising standardized sterile kits, a QR-enabled checklist, weekly competency training, and audit-feedback was implemented in January 2023.

Contamination was defined according to College of American Pathologists and American Society for Microbiology criteria. Rates were analyzed using risk ratios (RR), Fisher's exact test, and statistical process control (SPC) p-charts.

Results

Among 7,224 cultures, contamination decreased from 5.48% (2022) to 2.56% (2023) and 1.60% (2024). Compared with baseline, contamination risk declined by 53% in 2023 (RR 0.47; 95% CI 0.35–0.62) and 71% in 2024 (RR 0.29; 95% CI 0.19–0.44). SPC analysis demonstrated special-cause variation within two months of bundle implementation. Bundle fidelity improved from 85% to 97%.

Conclusion

A low-cost, nurse-driven aseptic technique bundle significantly reduced BCC and sustained performance below the <3% benchmark. The intervention provides a scalable and sustainable model for emergency departments in Oman and similar healthcare settings in the Gulf region.

INTRODUCTION

Blood cultures are essential for diagnosing bacteremia in children. However, contamination from skin flora leads to false positives, unnecessary antibiotics, repeat sampling, and increased costs [3]. International benchmarks from CAP and

ASM recommend contamination rates below 3% [8]. However, pediatric emergency departments often exceed this threshold due to technical challenges, urgent workflows, and variable staff experience.

Baseline audits in our Pediatric Emergency Department (PED) revealed contamination rates of 5.48% in 2022. To address this, we implemented a structured nurse-led intervention bundle in January 2023.

Methods

Study Design and Setting

Quasi-experimental before-after quality improvement study (January 2022–December 2024). Pre-intervention period: 2022. Post-intervention: 2023–2024.

The intervention was implemented within a tertiary pediatric emergency department with approximately 15,229 annual visits and 40 nursing staff.

Ethical Considerations

This study was approved by the Scientific Research Committee (SRC), Royal Hospital, Oman (MOH/25/29079).

Population

All pediatric patients (0–13 years) undergoing blood culture collection in the PED. Cultures drawn outside the PED or not meeting CAP/ASM contamination definitions were excluded.

Contamination Definition

Contamination was defined according to the 2024 College of American Pathologists (CAP) and American Society for Microbiology (ASM) evidence-based guidelines, as isolation of typical skin commensals (e.g., coagulase-negative Staphylococci, Corynebacterium spp., Bacillus spp. [non-anthraxis], Micrococcus spp., Cutibacterium acnes) in a single bottle without clinical correlation [8].

Intervention bundle

Standardized sterile kits, QR-enabled digital

checklist, weekly competency training, and audit-feedback. The bundle was co-designed with senior nurses to ensure feasibility and ownership.

Intervention Details

The nurse-led aseptic bundle was introduced in January 2023. Senior nurse educators conducted weekly 30-minute competency-based training sessions, reinforced by real-time audit-feedback. Audits were performed weekly, with results shared via dashboard reports. A laminated and QR-enabled checklist was used at the point of care to standardize aseptic technique. Standardized sterile kits were distributed to reduce supply variability.

Process Measures (Adherence and Fidelity)

Four fidelity indicators were tracked to assess adherence to the nurse-led aseptic blood culture collection bundle:

- Training coverage: Percentage of nurses completing weekly competency-based training.
- Checklist adherence: Proportion of blood culture collections performed with full compliance to the QR-enabled digital checklist.
- Kit utilization: Frequency of standardized sterile blood-culture kit use during sampling.
- Overall fidelity: Composite measure reflecting adherence across all bundle components.

Results of Process Measures:

Fidelity improved markedly over the study period. Training coverage increased from 60% at baseline to >95% in 2024. Checklist adherence rose from 70% to 90%, kit utilization improved from 80% to >99%, and overall fidelity advanced from 85% to 97%. These improvements paralleled the sustained reduction in contamination rates.

Table 1. Implementation Fidelity Indicators

Indicator	Baseline (%)	2024 (%)
Training coverage	60	95
Checklist compliance	70	90
Kit utilization	80	99
Overall adherence	85	97

Table 1. Fidelity indicators for the aseptic blood culture collection bundle. Training coverage, checklist adherence, kit utilization, and overall fidelity improved markedly from baseline in early 2023 to post-implementation in 2024.

Outcome Measures

- **Primary outcome:** Annual and monthly contamination rate.

Balancing measures

Balancing measures such as delays in culture collection, repeated venipunctures, or workflow disruptions were not formally measured. Although informal monitoring did not identify adverse effects, the absence of structured balancing data limits assessment of unintended consequences.

Statistical Analysis:

Descriptive statistics were used to summarize annual blood culture volumes and contamination rates. Annual contamination rates were compared using risk ratios (RR) with 95% confidence intervals and Fisher’s exact test was used to assess statistical significance.

Monthly contamination rates were analyzed using statistical process control (SPC) p- charts, a validated method for identifying special-cause variation and sustained process changes in healthcare quality improvement. Baseline centerlines and three-sigma control limits were calculated from pre-intervention data, and the timing of the intervention was annotated on SPC charts [9,10].

Western Electric rules were applied to detect special-cause variation, defined as eight

consecutive points below the centerline.

Implementation Timeline

- January 2023: Bundle launch and initial training.
- February 2023: Weekly audits and dashboard feedback initiated.
- March–December 2023: Fidelity monitoring and reinforcement.
- January–December 2024: Sustained monitoring with >95% training coverage and >97% overall fidelity.

Results

A total of 7,224 blood cultures were collected during the study period. Annual contamination rates declined from 5.48% in 2022 to 2.56% in 2023 and 1.60% in 2024, corresponding to 132, 59, and 40 contaminated cultures, respectively. Compared with baseline, contamination risk decreased by 53% in 2023 (RR 0.47; 95% CI, 0.35–0.62; P<.001) and 71% in 2024 (RR 0.29; 95% CI, 0.19–0.44; P<.001). The SPC p-chart (Figure 1) demonstrated special-cause variation within two months of bundle implementation, with a sustained downward shift and stable performance below the international benchmark of <3%. Annual contamination rates are summarized in Figure 2. Fidelity indicators improved markedly, with training coverage exceeding 95%, checklist adherence approaching 90%, kit utilization >99%, and overall fidelity reaching 97% (Table 1). These process improvements paralleled the sustained reduction in contamination rates (Table 2).

Table 2. Blood Culture Volume and Contamination Rates

Year	Total Cultures	Contaminated Cultures	Contamination Rate (%)
2022	2407	132	5.48
2023	2303	59	2.56
2024	2514	40	1.60

SPC Analysis

The SPC p-chart demonstrated special-cause variation within two months of bundle

implementation, with a sustained downward shift and stable performance below the international benchmark of <3%.

Figure 1. Statistical process control (SPC) chart of monthly pediatric blood culture contamination rates in the emergency department, January 2022 through December 2024. The centerline and three-sigma control limits were calculated from pre-intervention data. The vertical marker indicates the introduction of the nurse-led aseptic bundle in January 2023.

Overall Trends

A total of 7,224 blood cultures were collected.

Contamination decreased from 5.48% (2022) to 2.56% (2023) and 1.60% (2024) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Annual pediatric blood culture contamination rates in the emergency department, 2022–2024. Rates declined from 5.48% in 2022 to 2.56% in 2023 and 1.60% in 2024, demonstrating sustained improvement following bundle implementation.

Statistical Comparisons

Compared with baseline (2022), the risk of blood culture contamination decreased

significantly in both 2023 and 2024. The reduction was sustained in 2024 compared with 2023 (Table 3).

Table 3. Comparison of blood culture contamination risk between study periods

Comparison	Risk Ratio (RR)	95% CI	p value
2023 vs 2022	0.47	0.35–0.62	<0.001
2024 vs 2022	0.29	0.19–0.44	<0.001
2024 vs 2023	0.61	0.38–0.96	0.03

Discussion

This initiative achieved a 71% relative reduction in contamination, sustained over two years. Findings align with international reductions of 40–70% reported in bundled interventions [4,7]. Regional studies demonstrated reductions from approximately 5% to 2% after nurse-led protocols [2]. High implementation fidelity (97%) has likely contributed to sustained success.

Why the Intervention Worked

- Standardized kits reduced supply variability
- Checklists and QR-based prompts reduced cognitive load
- Weekly training and audit-feedback reinforced correct technique
- Nurse leadership ensured ownership and sustainability

Role of Fidelity in Driving Improvement

The high and sustained implementation fidelity (approximately 97%) likely contributed significantly to the durability of contamination reduction. Unlike interventions relying solely on passive education, this initiative incorporated continuous competency reinforcement, real-time audit-feedback, and digital checklist tracking. Evidence suggests that bundled interventions achieve optimal effectiveness when adherence exceeds 90%, which was consistently achieved in this study. The strong alignment between process performance and outcome improvement strengthens the causal inference of the intervention's effectiveness.

Comparison With Literature

The present study demonstrated a reduction in blood culture contamination (BCC) from 5.48% to 1.60%, representing a 71% relative risk reduction (RR 0.29; 95% CI 0.19–0.44) sustained over two years. This magnitude of improvement compares favorably with both regional and international literature.

Internationally, bundled interventions in emergency departments have demonstrated relative reductions ranging between 40% and 70% [4,5,7]. In a multicenter U.S. emergency department study, Self WH et al. reported a reduction from 4.3% to 1.7% ($\approx 60\%$ relative reduction) following implementation of standardized collection protocols and feedback systems [4]. Similarly, Gupta I and Codd demonstrated a decrease from 3.8% to 1.2% ($\approx 68\%$ reduction) using structured aseptic bundles [5]. A recent systematic review by Sautter RL et al. reported pooled reductions of 45–65%, particularly in institutions employing standardized kits and ongoing audit-feedback mechanisms [7].

Baseline contamination in our department (5.48%) was consistent with international pre-intervention ranges of 4–6% reported in emergency settings [3,4]. Importantly, our sustained two-year performance contrasts with some studies where early improvement regressed once active monitoring was diminished. The durability observed in our study likely reflects high

implementation fidelity (97%), weekly competency reinforcement, and real-time dashboard feedback. Regionally, limited published pediatric data exists from the Gulf region. A recent Omani epidemiological study by Al Saeghi N et al. described bloodstream infection patterns but did not evaluate contamination reduction strategies [1]. Therefore, this study provides one of the first structured, longitudinal QI evaluations of pediatric BCC reduction in Oman and contributes important regional data.

Overall, our 71% relative reduction lies at the upper range of internationally reported outcomes, supports the effectiveness of nurse-led aseptic bundles, and demonstrates that high-income country benchmarks are achievable within Gulf-region tertiary centers using low-cost system redesign.

Clinical and System Impact

Although secondary outcomes were not formally measured, reduced contamination is expected to decrease unnecessary antibiotic exposure, repeated venipunctures, false-positive sepsis evaluations, laboratory workload, and parental anxiety. These benefits warrant future study.

Strengths and Limitations

Strengths include a large sample size, three-year duration, CAP/ASM-aligned definitions, and robust process and outcome measures. Limitations include the single-center, non-randomized design and lack of formal measurement of secondary outcomes such as antibiotic use and cost savings. Balancing measures such as delays in culture collection or repeated venipunctures were not formally measured, which limits assessment of unintended consequences.

Implications

This low-cost, nurse-driven model is feasible, scalable, and well-suited for replication across emergency departments in Oman and the wider Gulf region. Future multicenter studies could strengthen generalizability and enable national benchmarking.

Conclusion

Implementation of a structured, nurse-led aseptic sampling bundle in a tertiary pediatric emergency department achieved and sustained a >70% reduction in blood culture contamination, maintaining rates below the international benchmark of <3% for two consecutive years. High fidelity to bundle components was critical to success. This low-cost, scalable model offers a practical pathway for improving diagnostic reliability and patient safety across emergency departments in Oman and the wider Gulf region.

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